

Table 2. Seed set on cms lines due to cross-pollination with maintainers and elite lines, O Mon, Hau Giang, Vietnam.

Cross	Seed set (%) on cms lines
<i>1983 wet season</i>	
V20A/V20B	4
Zhen Shan 97A/Zhen Shan 91B	2
V20A/NN3A (IR36)	10
V20A/NN4B (IR42)	3
V20A/IR54	2
97A/NN3A	9
97A/NN4B	2
97A/IR54	4
<i>1984 dry season</i>	
V20A/V20B	43
Zhen Shan 97 A/Zhen Shan 97B	36
V20A/NN3A	21
V20A/NN6A (IR2307.247.2.2.3)	30
V20A/IR56	32
V20A/OM33 (IR9224.73.2.2.2.3)	26
V20A/IR8423.132.6.2.2	34
V20A/NN7A (IR9129.192.2.3.5)	35
97A/NN3 A	35
97A/NN6A	33
97A/IR56	41
97A/OM33	26
97A/IR8423	35
97A/NN7 A	40

less panicles/m², and high sterility (Table 1). The maintainers had high 1,000-grain weight. V20B and Zhen Shan 97B yielded less than 3 t/ha in both seasons. The lines were resistant to blast but highly susceptible to stem borer and sheath rot. Panicles of cms plants often showed incomplete exertion.

Outcrossing pollination between cms lines, maintainers, and some elite lines was evaluated in the greenhouse in 1983 wet season and in the field in 1984 dry season. Female-to-male ratio was 4:1. Twenty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Maintainers were sown 5 d later than cms lines and sowing time of elite lines was adjusted to synchronize flowering. Ropes were pulled across plots to encourage cross-pollination, but we did not clip leaves or apply gibberellic acid to improve panicle exertion.

Filled and unfilled grains were counted on 20 plants of each cms line. Cross pollination was 2-10% in wet season and 21-43% in dry season (Table 2). *S*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization TISSUE CULTURE

Phylogenetic mutation for grain type in japonica rice after mutagen treatment of fertilized egg cells

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Fertilized egg cells of japonica Taichung 65 were treated with 0.5 or 1.0 mM N-methyl N-nitrosourea (MNU) 12 h after anthesis by panicle dipping method for 1, 2, and 3 h. Each treatment had 500 fertilized egg cells. Seeds from treated panicles were harvested 40 d after treatment and the M₁ was planted in the field.

Mutants with indica grain type (length:breadth >2.0) are shown in Table 1, and grain characters of some mutants are in Table 2. Length:breadth of grains of indica mutants was 2.71 to 3.47, compared to the parent ratio of 1.72.

Different grain types of mutants. 1 = parent, 2 = long grain, 3 = awned spikelets.

Table 1. Frequency of progenies with indica grain type in M₁ population.

MNU treatment	M ₁ plants (no.) tested	M ₁ plants (no.) with indica grain type	Frequency (%)
Control (water)	200	0	0.000
0.5 mM for 1 h	510	0	0.000
2 h	1261	9	0.714
3 h	577	2	0.347
1.0 mM for 1 h	540	4	0.740
2 h	881	11	1.248
3 h	512	3	0.586

Table 2. Grain characters of indica mutants in M₁.

Mutant line	Grain size (mm) (length × breadth)	Length:breadth	100-grain weight (g)
T3 - 995	7.01 × 2.25	3.11	2.0
T4 - 1462	7.14 × 2.06	3.47	2.2
T5 - 2020	6.23 × 2.27	2.74	2.0
T5 - 2123	6.29 × 2.28	2.76	2.1
T6 - 2282	7.20 × 2.12	3.40	2.2
T6 - 2284	6.96 × 2.08	3.35	2.0
T6 - 2396	2.96 × 2.04	3.41	2.1
T6 - 2423	6.13 × 2.26	2.71	2.0
T7 - 2974	6.33 × 2.29	2.77	2.1
T7 - 2918	5.64 × 2.03	2.78	1.6
Parent	5.00 × 2.91	1.72	2.4

The figure shows grain size of the panicles of indica mutants and the parent. Sixty seeds from each mutant progeny were planted and their grain

shape evaluated. Grain shape did not segregate.

Similar changes in grain type have been reported to be induced by mutagen

treatment of seeds. Such phylogenetic mutants can help understand differentiation and evolutionary relationships among rice genotypes. *J*

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Cow dung extract for controlling bacterial blight (BB)

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* is becoming a serious pest in Kerala. In 1982-83, we compared cow dung and urine with recommended antibiotics for controlling BB.

Susceptible Triveni and Cul. 1907 were planted at 15- × 10-cm spacing in 4.95- × 2.10-m plots in 4 replications. NPK was applied at 70-35-35 kg/ha.

Five foliar sprays were applied 10 and 15 days after clip inoculation of BB at maximum tillering, cow dung slurry was topdressed, and cow dung was applied

Different treatments for controlling BB, Pattambi, India.

Treatment	Dose/ha	Disease index (%)		
		Triveni		Cul. 1907
		1982 kharif	1982-83 rabi	1983 kharif
Penicillin (100 ppm)	50 g	38	22	31
Paushamycin (250 ppm)	750 g	37	42	26
Streptomycin (100 ppm)	500 g	39	19	32
Cow dung extract (20 g/litre)	10 kg	41	25	26
Cow urine (20 ml/litre)	10 litres	50	31	45
Cow dung slurry topdressing	5 t	43	36	31
Cow dung basal application	10 t	46	32	44
Untreated check	-	62	50	75
CD (P = 0.05)	-			

basally. Disease reaction was scored by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* on the 3 top leaves of 10 randomly selected plants in each treatment.

A foliar spray of cow dung extract (20 g/litre) controlled BB as well as penicillin, paushamycin, and streptomycin (see table). *J*

Effect of fertilizers, nutrients, and soil amendments on tungro virus (RTV)

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In Oct 84-Jan 85 we studied the effect of fertilizers, nutrients, and soil amendments on RTV at TNRRI. AD36364 was planted in a field experiment with seven treatments with four replications arranged in a randomized block design. At 20 and 35 d after transplanting, ammonium chloride, ammonium sulfate, and urea were topdressed in equal splits at 50 kg N/ha and diammonium phosphate and Zn sulfate were applied as foliar sprays at 3 and 5% concentration. Lime was applied between plant rows at 500 kg/ha. No insecticide was applied.

Effect of fertilizers, nutrients, and soil amendments on RTV infection, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	RTV infection (%)		Yield (t/ha)
	Initial	Final	
	Ammonium chloride (50 kg N/ha)	43	
Ammonium sulfate (50 kg N/ha)	44	77	1.6
Urea (50 kg N/ha)	48	76	1.5
Diammonium phosphate (3% spray)	51	72	1.7
Zn sulfate (5% spray)	45	76	1.5
Lime (500 kg/ha)	48	78	1.5
Control (no treatment)	47	79	1.4

Percent RTV infection and yield are in the table.

Average RTV infection, assessed visually and by iodine test, increased uniformly in all treatments and reached 79%. There were significant differences in plant height. Plants that received

diammonium phosphate and ammonium sulfate grew tallest. There were no significant differences in yield, but plots with diammonium phosphate yielded highest. *J*

Chemical control of blast (BI) in Punjab, Pakistan

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BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. seriously damages rice in Punjab. To evaluate and demonstrate chemical control of BI and generate adaptive research recommendations, we tested two chemicals at two application rates (see table) for BI control in replicated experiments at AARF and three